
Building Socially Grounded Multi-Agent LLM Systems Requires the Transition from Static LLM Prompting to Autonomous Multi-Agent Ecosystems

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Abstract

This paper argues that many limitations attributed to Large Language Models (LLMs) as models are better understood as limitations of how they are deployed as systems. Static prompting of isolated, stateless text generators systematically excludes the temporal continuity, feedback, and adaptation that define social mechanisms. We offer a structured perspective grounded in social science theory: a Six-Level Continuum of agentic complexity that links architectural commitments to validity targets for social simulation. The framework provides a shared vocabulary for principled system selection, specifying which architectural features are required to instantiate which social mechanisms. We conclude by calling for closer collaboration between machine learning researchers and social scientists to co-design agentic systems that are not only technically capable, but also socially meaningful.

1. Introduction

How should the machine learning community advance LLM-based agentic systems? Recent progress in reasoning, planning, and coordination has been substantial (Guozhen et al., 2024; Anthis et al., 2025), yet debate persists about whether LLMs can meaningfully model human behavior and social dynamics. We argue that many limitations attributed to LLMs *as models* are better understood as limitations of how LLMs are *deployed as systems*. The dominant paradigm says that static prompting of isolated, stateless text generators systematically excludes the temporal continuity, feedback, and adaptation that define social mechanisms. This is not a claim that current models are sufficient; it is a claim that architectural choices, not only model capabilities, determine what agentic systems can represent.

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This paper offers one way forward: grounding the design of agentic systems in social science theory. We do not claim to invent social agents as such, because multi-agent LLM systems already exist, and encouraging progress toward agentic architectures is underway (Park et al., 2023; Piao et al., 2025; Dai et al., 2024). However, these efforts remain fragmented and lack a shared vocabulary for reasoning about what different system designs can and cannot do. Our contribution is a *structured perspective* on what to study and how: a design framework that makes explicit which architectural commitments are required to instantiate which social mechanisms, and which validity criteria are appropriate at each level of complexity.

Static prompting has proven effective for well-scoped tasks such as coding qualitative data (Kantor, 2024), summarizing literature (Hardy et al., 2023; Demszky et al., 2023), or generating survey responses (Ziems et al., 2024; Karjus, 2025). Social phenomena such as radicalization, negotiation, coordination, and market dynamics do not arise from isolated decisions. They emerge through iterative, path-dependent interaction shaped by memory, goals, and mutual adaptation. Systems that forget prior interactions and lack agency are *epistemically incapable* of capturing these processes: they lack the temporal state, goal structure, and feedback mechanisms required to instantiate them (Wang et al., 2024). This gap reflects a deeper mismatch between the tools we build and the phenomena we seek to understand. Current practices rely on stateless models to explain a decidedly *stateful* world (Epstein, 1999; Park et al., 2023; Lu et al., 2024). The limitations of static prompting are therefore not merely methodological inconveniences for social scientists; they are *architectural constraints* that restrict the real-world relevance of agentic AI systems more broadly.

Social science provides precisely what the field currently lacks: a systematic account of which mechanisms matter for social dynamics and what properties systems must have to instantiate them. Decades of work in Psychology, Economics, and Sociology have characterized how memory, path dependence, feedback, and coordination produce macro-level phenomena from micro-level interaction. This theoretical grounding tells us what agentic systems *need* to do, like maintain persistent state, pursue goals, respond

to consequences, coordinate with others, and thus what architectural commitments are required. Machine learning research on agentic systems should shift from static prompting and sandboxed single-agent setups toward socially grounded Multi-Agent LLM Systems (MAS) with persistent state, goal pursuit, and environment coupling, co-designed with social science expertise. Such collaboration is essential because social behavior is inherently stateful: it depends on memory, temporality, agency, and feedback between agents and their environments. Without these properties, increasingly sophisticated agentic architectures risk remaining disconnected from the social dynamics they are intended to model and support.

This paper makes three contributions:

1. **A diagnostic reframing:** We argue that socially meaningful phenomena require repeated closure of a decision cycle at the system level, because social mechanisms depend on history, feedback, and mutual adaptation rather than isolated outputs. Many current limitations are architectural, not model-inherent.
2. **A design framework:** We introduce a Six-Level Continuum of agentic complexity that links architectural commitments (persistent state, goal pursuit, environment coupling, coordination, adaptation) to validity targets and failure modes relevant for social simulation (Haase & Pokutta, 2025; Feng et al., 2025; Starace et al., 2025; Estornell & Liu, 2024).
3. **A shared vocabulary for interdisciplinary collaboration:** The framework supports principled system selection by specifying, for a given targeted social mechanism, which architectural commitments are minimally required and which validity and robustness checks are warranted. This vocabulary is intended to enable productive collaboration between machine learning researchers and social scientists, which we deem prerequisite for building MAS with real-world relevance.

Recent work argues that LLM social simulations are promising if five tractable challenges are addressed: diversity, bias, sycophancy, alienness, and generalization (Anthis et al., 2025). Our position is complementary: rather than organizing the space by prompting and tuning techniques, we organize by system architecture and decision-loop closure. Several of these challenges become *structural* when systems lack persistent state, environment coupling, and interaction protocols. We differ from broad agent surveys (Guozhen et al., 2024) by focusing specifically on a design vocabulary for socially grounded multi-agent ecosystems and provide a roadmap for engineering systems capable of modeling interaction, coordination, and emergence at scale.

The scope of this paper is LLM-based systems for social

simulation and social science research workflows. The framework guides design and evaluation alignment: it helps researchers map a targeted social mechanism to minimal architectural commitments and corresponding validity checks. Several boundaries apply: the framework is not a benchmarking instrument, maturity model, or normative claim that higher complexity is always preferable. For coding, summarization, or controlled response generation, static prompting remains appropriate. We do not claim human equivalence for any level of the continuum, and we do not offer a safety certification scheme for open-ended systems.

2. Why Static LLM Architectures Limit Socially Meaningful Agentic Systems

The rapid progress of agentic AI has been enabled by deliberate architectural simplifications. Isolated agents, static environments, and task-specific sandboxes have allowed researchers to debug components, establish benchmarks, and study individual capabilities such as reasoning, planning, and tool use under controlled conditions. This phase was not a failure of ambition. On the contrary, architectural sandboxing was an essential prerequisite for early advances in agentic systems, mirroring earlier stages in fields such as reinforcement learning, robotics, and agent-based modeling.

However, as the field increasingly targets sustained interaction, coordination, and real-world deployment, these same constraints have become a limiting factor. A central obstacle is low behavioral diversity: LLM outputs can be highly homogeneous even in simple strategic settings, producing narrow action distributions that diverge from human variability (Anthis et al., 2025). Recent work argues that most current simulations remain confined to static sandboxes characterized by predefined tasks, limited dynamics, and rigid evaluation criteria, which fundamentally suppress emergence and adaptation (Chen et al., 2025). In settings where agents are expected to interact over time, influence one another, and reshape their environment, architectures optimized for isolation and short-horizon performance are structurally misaligned with socially meaningful agentic systems—that is, systems whose behavior maps onto social science constructs through temporally extended interaction, memory, and feedback rather than surface-level imitation.

Recent empirical work provides proof-of-concept that LLM-based simulations can match nontrivial human experimental regularities under specific conditions (Anthis et al., 2025), motivating a shift toward reality-bounded Multi-Agent LLM Systems (MAS): systems whose dynamics are constrained by interaction histories, environment rules, and endogenous feedback, excluding degrees of freedom that would make mechanisms uninterpretable (Guo et al., 2024; Tran et al., 2025).

2.1. Architectural Sandboxing and the Limits of Isolated Agents

A dominant design pattern across many LLM-based systems treats agents as isolated cognitive units that map inputs to outputs within tightly constrained environments. Even when framed as “agents”, these systems often operate with fixed task definitions, shallow temporal horizons, and limited interaction channels. Such sandboxing offers clear benefits: it improves reproducibility, simplifies evaluation, and allows researchers to study components in isolation. These advantages explain why static sandboxed architectures have become the default in much contemporary work, including applications in computational social science where LLMs are used for coding, summarization, or controlled response generation.

Yet, as Chen et al. (Chen et al., 2025) argue, static sandboxed architectures are fundamentally inadequate for modeling societal complexity. Social systems are not characterized by fixed tasks or stationary dynamics, but by continuous adaptation, mutual influence, and structural change. When environments remain static and agent actions do not accumulate consequences over time, the system is prevented from exhibiting co-evolutionary dynamics. As a result, core properties of social systems—including emergence, feedback, and learning—are excluded by design rather than by limitation of the underlying models.

Architectural sandboxing manifests in three interlocking deficits that systematically limit socially meaningful agentic systems.

Deficit 1: Temporal continuity. Social behavior is inherently path-dependent. Human decisions are shaped by accumulated histories, evolving expectations, and long-term consequences. Static LLM deployments, however, typically reset state between interactions or retain only shallow conversational context. This precludes modeling longitudinal mechanisms such as reputation formation, trust building, escalation, or radicalization trajectories. Without persistent memory and temporal grounding, social dynamics collapse into disconnected snapshots rather than unfolding processes. The importance of memory, state, and long-horizon interaction is widely recognized in recent discussions of agentic LLM design (Wang et al., 2024; Park et al., 2023), yet remains absent from many sandboxed systems.

Deficit 2: Agency. Social systems are driven by proactive, goal-directed behavior. Humans initiate interaction, pursue objectives, and strategically adapt to others. In contrast, many prompt-based architectures remain fundamentally reactive: they respond to external queries but do not autonomously decide when or how to act. This limits their ability to generate endogenous interaction patterns that give

rise to macro-social phenomena such as norm formation, coalition building, or institutional change. Evidence from other domains demonstrates that this limitation is not inherent to LLMs. In chemistry, for example, LLM-based agents already orchestrate complex workflows by autonomously planning, executing, and evaluating experimental protocols (Boiko et al., 2023; Guo et al., 2024). These systems illustrate that agents can be designed to conduct multi-step processes rather than merely respond to prompts, providing a concrete blueprint for agentic social simulation.

Deficit 3: Environmental interaction. Social behavior is situated and embedded. Actors both influence and are influenced by their environment, and many social dynamics arise from feedback loops between agent behavior and changing environmental conditions. In sandboxed systems, environments are often static backdrops with limited action spaces, preventing meaningful agent–environment coupling. As Chen et al. (Chen et al., 2025) emphasize, modeling societal complexity requires open-ended co-evolution, in which agents and environments adapt to one another over time. Without such coupling, systems cannot exhibit adaptation, co-evolution, or emergence, regardless of the sophistication of individual agent models.

Architectural sandboxing is a necessary stage for isolating and validating agentic components, but it also removes the core ingredients of social dynamics. As the field now targets increasingly complex forms of interaction and coordination, static and isolated architectures have become the primary bottleneck. Advancing agentic AI therefore requires expanding beyond sandboxed settings toward MAS embedded in adaptive environments.

2.2. Why Social Simulation Requires Agentic Systems

The motivation for agentic social simulation is epistemic, not merely practical. Many socially consequential phenomena—radicalization, coordinated misinformation, institutional collapse—cannot ethically be manipulated in real-world populations, limiting researchers to observational analyses that obscure mechanisms. Agentic simulation offers a principled alternative: controlled experiments at scale, including counterfactual testing and high-throughput variation of initial conditions (Anthis et al., 2025). Recent work demonstrates how decentralized agent interactions can give rise to governance structures and coordination equilibria (Dai et al., 2024; Piatti et al., 2024; Piao et al., 2025). Critically, such experimentation requires agents with memory, goal pursuit, interaction, and adaptation—properties that static prompting architectures structurally exclude.

These limitations motivate a transition from isolated prompting toward socially grounded multi-agent ecosystems. The following section introduces a structured continuum of agen-

Figure 1. MAS through the Observe–Orient–Decide–Act (OODA) loop. Static prompting implements isolated action generation, whereas MAS close decision loops via observation, memory and orientation, planning and decision, and action within an environment. Scaling closed loops across interacting agents enables system level dynamics relevant for social simulation.

tic complexity that provides a design roadmap for building systems capable of valid social simulation.

3. A Roadmap for Agency: The Six-Level Continuum

Moving beyond static sandboxed architectures requires a shared vocabulary for reasoning about increasing levels of agency, interaction, and social complexity. We propose a Six-Level Continuum of agentic complexity as a *design roadmap* for the machine learning community, delineating qualitatively distinct system classes characterized by specific architectural commitments and epistemic affordances. The continuum links agentic complexity to validity targets and failure modes relevant for social simulation.

The continuum aligns with Boyd’s Observe–Orient–Decide–Act (OODA) loop (Boyd, 2018). The OODA loop provides a useful abstraction for agentic behavior because it makes explicit the difference between reactive output generation and temporally extended decision-making. *Observation* refers to acquiring new information from the environment or other agents; *orientation* integrates this information with prior beliefs, memory, and goals; *decision* selects a course of action based on this internal state; and *action* executes that decision, altering the environment and future observations. Social interaction depends not on isolated actions, but on repeated closure of this loop over time (Figure 1, Table 1). Static prompting implements only the *Act* phase; higher levels progressively close the loop through memory, goal orientation, environmental coupling, coordination, and adaptation. Systems that implement only the action phase cannot accumulate history or adapt strategies, making them structurally incapable of modeling interactional dynamics.

3.1. Levels 0–1: Tools and Isolated Roles

At Levels 0 and 1, LLMs are primarily used as tools for text processing or as role-conditioned responders. These systems are widely deployed for tasks such as qualitative coding

Phase	Mechanism	Observable artifact
Observe	environment input, tool output, message reception	event log, retrieved documents, sensor or API outputs
Orient	memory retrieval, belief or state update, goal conditioning	updated state representation, memory write, retrieved summaries
Decide	planning, scoring, action selection policy	ranked actions, selected plan, decision trace
Act	tool execution, message emission, environment action	tool call record, environment state update, emitted actions

Table 1. Operational mapping from OODA phases to mechanisms and inspectable artifacts in LLM based agent systems.

(Ziems et al., 2024), text quantification (Karjus, 2025), and controlled persona simulation (Argyle et al., 2023). Their strength lies in efficiency, consistency, and ease of evaluation. As such, they play an important role in augmenting human research workflows and reducing analytical overhead.

However, these systems possess no endogenous agency. Even when persona prompts are used, behavior remains reactive and stateless or only weakly stateful. Opinions do not evolve across interactions, and actions do not accumulate consequences. As a result, Level 0 and 1 systems are methodologically safe but theoretically sterile with respect to social dynamics. They can assist social scientists, but they cannot simulate social processes.

3.2. Levels 2–3: Individual Agents

Levels 2 and 3 introduce autonomous agency at the level of the individual. Systems at these levels possess goals, control logic, and the ability to maintain persistent internal state. Examples include survey agents that browse the web or interact with tools (Wang et al., 2024), as well as generative agents endowed with long-term memory and planning capabilities (Park et al., 2023). Such agents can reproduce certain exper-

Multi-Agent LLM Systems Need to Move Beyond Static Prompting

Lvl	System Type	Threshold Criterion	OODA Coverage	Primary Design Challenge	Typical Failure Mode	Tooling & Evaluation Implications
<i>Tools</i>						
0	LLM-as-Tool	(baseline)	Act	Reliable text generation	Snapshot bias; no state	Prompt engineering; task-level accuracy
1	LLM-as-Role	Memory integration	Observe → Act	Persona consistency	Persona drift; shallow memory	Session memory; consistency checks
<i>Agents</i>						
2	Agent-like LLM	Goal-driven autonomy	Observe → Orient → Act	Action selection	Goal incoherence; prompt overfitting	Control logic; trajectory evaluation
3	Fully agentic	Environment interface	Full OODA loop	Strategic reasoning	Memory collapse; tool misuse	Persistent memory; tool grounding
<i>Societies</i>						
4	Multi-agent	Coordination	OODA + Learn	Inter-agent alignment	Coordination failure; instability	Orchestration layers; group metrics
5	Complex adaptive	Emergence	Dynamic OODA + Evolve	System-level stability	Runaway dynamics; norm drift	Population-level evaluation; robustness

Table 2. A design-oriented continuum of agentic complexity adapted from (Haase & Pokutta, 2025). This version emphasizes system design challenges, failure modes, and tooling implications relevant to machine learning researchers developing socially grounded MAS.

imental patterns observed in human subjects (Horton, 2023), indicating a degree of psychological plausibility.

Level 3 requires that action consequences are represented as environment state updates that persist across steps, enabling iterative replanning. Level 3 represents the minimal threshold for psychological validity. Importantly, it does not imply human equivalence, but sufficient internal coherence to instantiate theoretically meaningful decision and interaction mechanisms. An agent that cannot remember prior interactions or plan future actions cannot meaningfully approximate human behavior. From a system design perspective, this level requires explicit design commitments to memory persistence, environment interfaces, and autonomous decision cycles. Importantly, while Level 3 agents can model individual cognition, they remain insufficient for capturing social phenomena that arise from interaction between multiple actors.

3.3. Levels 4–5: Multi-Agent Societies

Social science is fundamentally concerned with interaction. Levels 4 and 5 therefore represent the target regime for socially meaningful agentic systems. At Level 4, multiple agents interact within a shared environment, coordinate actions, and negotiate roles and goals. Early successes include systems such as *AI Scientist* (Lu et al., 2024) and *PaperBench* (Starace et al., 2025), where agents assume differentiated roles and collaboratively solve complex tasks. These architectures enable the study of coordination dynam-

ics, polarization, and collaborative problem-solving in ways that static prompting cannot (Estornell & Liu, 2024; Xu et al., 2024; Li et al., 2023).

Level 5 extends this paradigm to complex adaptive systems, where macro-level social structures emerge from decentralized interaction. Here, norms, institutions, and collective behavior arise endogenously rather than being predefined. Such an autonomous multi agent ecosystem is a multi agent system in which agents repeatedly execute closed decision cycles over time (observe, orient, decide, act), while interacting in a shared environment with persistent state. The term “ecosystem” indicates that system behavior is shaped by endogenous feedback between agents and environment, so trajectories depend on interaction history rather than being reset each turn or each episode. Examples like work on emergent governance demonstrates how agents can evolve social contracts from a state of nature (Dai et al., 2024), while studies of resource governance show the spontaneous formation of cooperative norms (Piatti et al., 2024). These systems operationalize the type of open-ended co-evolution that static sandboxes explicitly preclude (Chen et al., 2025). Traditional agent-based modeling often abstracted away from the richness of human communication, while traditional LLM prompting abstracts away from interactional structure. Level 5 LLM-based multi-agent systems bridge this gap by combining expressive communication with dynamic social organization, offering the first viable sandbox for high-fidelity sociological theory testing (Gao et al., 2023).

3.4. Implications for System Design

The continuum clarifies that progress toward socially grounded agentic artificial intelligence is not primarily a matter of scaling model size. It requires explicit architectural commitments about (i) persistent state, (ii) autonomy and goal pursuit, (iii) coordination protocols, and (iv) environment dynamics. Each commitment changes what the system can represent, and therefore which social mechanisms the system can plausibly instantiate. As a result, the central design question becomes alignment between the targeted mechanism and the implemented architecture, rather than incremental improvements in isolated prompt performance.

Encouragingly, recent work already points toward this shift. Survey work frames a move toward “Collective AI,” emphasizing lifelong learning, knowledge sharing, and coordinated decision making across interacting components (Guo et al., 2024). In addition, multi agent debate and collaboration frameworks suggest that structured interaction among differentiated roles can improve factuality and robustness relative to isolated models, which supports the broader claim that coordination structure is a first class design variable rather than an application layer wrapper (Guo et al., 2024; Tran et al., 2025).

For machine learning researchers, the continuum therefore functions as a guide for tool development and system selection. Different research questions require different levels of agentic complexity, and mismatches between system design and target phenomena undermine validity. Designing socially meaningful agentic systems requires infrastructure for orchestration, memory, and environment coupling, together with explicit design documentation that makes these choices inspectable. Importantly, the relevant unit of design is often the interacting population rather than the isolated instance, because population level dynamics can be sensitive to coordination rules, information flow, and the constraints imposed by the environment.

3.5. Implications for Evaluation and Scientific Rigor

The continuum implies that scientific rigor in agentic systems depends on evaluating the full decision cycle, rather than only one shot task performance. As systems shift from static prompting toward persistent, interactive, and open ended settings, the appropriate unit of analysis changes. Evaluation must therefore be matched to the level of agentic complexity that the study claims to investigate.

Unit of analysis and validity targets. First, when an agent is treated as an isolated cognitive unit, evaluation can emphasize task outcomes together with the stability and coherence of decision behavior across time. In this regime, the relevant criterion is *psychological validity*, defined here as the degree to which an individual agent exhibits internally

coherent and temporally stable decision behavior that is sufficient to instantiate a targeted individual level mechanism, such as stable preferences, consistent memory use, goal pursuit, and planning. The key requirement is that coherence is not only internal, but also externally consistent with the theory specified mechanism. Beyond surface-level fit, simulations must address alienness: systems can reproduce broad empirical regularities while relying on non-human mechanisms that fail at finer-grained measurement levels. This motivates conceptual models and iterative evaluation that test latent and item-level constraints, rather than only aggregate agreement (Anthis et al., 2025).

Second, when agents are treated as interacting with one another, evaluation must move beyond individual performance to collective dynamics. In this regime, the relevant criterion is *sociological validity*, defined here as the degree to which a population of interacting agents in a shared environment reproduces theory specified macro level regularities under theory appropriate boundary conditions, and does so robustly under replication and sensitivity analysis. The key requirement is that collective behavior is not only coherent, but also externally consistent with the theory specified mechanism.

Third, when agents are treated as interacting with a society, evaluation must include societal level outcomes and failure modes, such as norm formation and norm drift, institutional stability and institutional breakdown, and distributional effects across groups. In this regime, rigor depends on whether macro level patterns persist across replications, remain resilient under perturbations, and remain interpretable given the stated theoretical assumptions and boundary conditions. Following Anthis et al. (2025), LLM social simulations are already useful for lower-stakes scientific functions such as pilot studies, exploratory studies, exact replication, and sensitivity analysis, while end-to-end complete studies remain a longer-term target. This staging aligns with our continuum: higher agentic levels increase both epistemic affordances and evaluation burdens, so method choice should follow the intended application.

Analytic flexibility as a central threat to rigor. As agentic systems become more interactive, the number of defensible analytic decisions increases sharply. Cummins (2025) shows that, even for comparatively simple silicon sample workflows, small changes in researcher choices can dramatically alter correspondence with human data, and that performance is often inconsistent across evaluation dimensions rather than improving uniformly (Gelman & Loken, 2013). This observation generalizes to agentic evaluations: apparent improvements in one metric can coincide with degradation in another, and conclusions can depend on choices such as model family, sampling settings, prompt structure, conditioning information, interaction protocol, or output handling

(Sclar et al., 2024; Zhang et al., 2025). The implication is that evaluation cannot be treated as a single score. It must be treated as a disciplined workflow with explicit constraints on researcher degrees of freedom.

Rigor requirements for agentic evaluations. To reduce analytic flexibility and strengthen inference, we propose the following minimum standards when drawing scientific conclusions from agentic systems. First, authors should *map and report* the key analytic decisions that can affect output, including model choice, sampling and reasoning parameters, prompting strategy, information provided, interaction protocol, environment rules, and output postprocessing (Cummins, 2025).

Second, authors should *pilot and iterate* evaluations against existing reference data when available, rather than relying on intuition about what should influence model behavior (Cummins, 2025; Bell et al., 2022).

Third, authors should quantify sensitivity to plausible alternatives. A practical tool is a *specification curve* style analysis that visualizes heterogeneity across plausible configurations and identifies which decisions exert the largest influence on results (Simonsohn et al., 2020; Bell et al., 2022).

Fourth, for generalization, the most direct test is prediction on genuinely novel data that postdates a model’s training cut-off or was unavailable at simulation time, ideally compared against human and expert forecasts (Anthis et al., 2025). Preregistration of simulation predictions, especially with expert forecasts, can mitigate publication bias and clarify where simulations generalize and where they fail.

Fifth, as the unit of analysis shifts from individuals to groups and societies, replication across random seeds and sensitivity analysis should become default practice, because robustness is a prerequisite for interpreting emergence as theoretically informative rather than incidental (Cummins, 2025).

Taken together, these standards align the continuum with a discipline of evaluation. Increasing agentic complexity does not relax scientific rigor. It increases the need for explicit reporting, sensitivity quantification, and theory aligned validity criteria, so that claims about socially grounded phenomena remain interpretable, reproducible, and defensible.

4. Alternative Views

To make this position robust, we address two credible objections that are likely to arise in the machine learning community when moving from tool like prompting toward socially grounded multi agent ecosystems: concerns about interpretability and experimental control, and concerns about safety and reliability in open ended interaction.

4.1. The “Tool First” Perspective: Control, Interpretability, and Scientific Isolation

A prevailing view holds that LLMs should remain tools rather than agents to preserve interpretability and experimental control. Once autonomy, memory, and agent to agent communication are introduced, the system can become harder to trace, harder to reproduce, and more prone to artifacts that are difficult to interpret. This concern is reinforced by the fact that much of current multi agent evaluation still takes place in static sandboxes, that is, closed environments with predefined tasks and narrow metrics that reward predictability over ecological realism (Chen et al., 2025).

Response: We agree with the motivation for sandboxing. Isolating components is often necessary to validate mechanisms, debug failure modes, and build trustworthy primitives. However, if the scientific goal is to study socially grounded mechanisms that are defined by adaptation over time, rigid benchmarks and predictable interaction loops can systematically suppress the phenomena of interest and can incentivize brittle systems (Chen et al., 2025). The methodological implication is not to abandon control, but to complement tool like baselines with evaluation paradigms that quantify longer horizon system properties, such as memory consistency, resilience, and coordination quality, rather than only task success (Chen et al., 2025).

4.2. The “Safety and Reliability” Perspective: Open Ended Multi Agent Ecosystems Are Uncontrollable

A second objection is that LLMs are probabilistic generators rather than reliable decision makers, and that coupling them into multi agent systems can amplify errors. One agent can introduce fabricated content that propagates through interaction, while memory drift and value misalignment can compound over time. Relatedly, open ended co evolution can be viewed as unsafe or scientifically uncontrollable, because agents and environments can produce unexpected behaviors that are difficult to bound, audit, and evaluate. Further, instruction-tuning can induce sycophancy, yielding outputs that are optimized for user approval rather than behavioral realism, analogous to social desirability bias in human subjects research (Anthis et al., 2025). As a result, models optimized as helpful assistants can be systematically worse simulators, which motivates explicit reporting of interaction framing and measures that detect approval-seeking artifacts. These concerns are widely discussed as recurring challenges in LLM based multi agent systems (Chen et al., 2025), and they motivate epistemological caution regarding what kinds of inferences such systems can support (Haase & Pokutta, 2025).

Response: We treat these failure modes as design constraints rather than conceptual deal breakers. The relevant

question is not whether errors, bias, or instability exist, but whether architectures and evaluation protocols can make error sources legible and bound their influence through grounding, verification, and interaction design (Chen et al., 2025). Practically, this implies shifting constraints upward: from narrowly task specific restrictions toward principled evaluation dimensions that reward robustness, long horizon memory consistency, and stability under perturbations, while still measuring diversity and adaptation when these are required by the target mechanism (Chen et al., 2025). It also implies a staged approach: the community should increase autonomy and openness only when evaluation protocols can measure system level risks, supported by environment constraints, audit trails, replication, and sensitivity analysis. Under this framing, safety concerns strengthen rather than invalidate our position. If the field is moving toward multi agent systems in the real world, then methodologically transparent ecosystems are needed to study and mitigate interaction driven harms, rather than to ignore them.

The mirroring argument. Several critiques raised against agentic LLM systems resemble long standing methodological critiques within social science. Formal models are criticized for abstraction, laboratory experiments for artificiality, surveys for framing effects, and qualitative methods for interpretive subjectivity.

Response: Social science has progressed not by eliminating these limitations, but by making them explicit and aligning method choice with the research question (Cartwright, 1989; Elster, 2015; Hedström & Ylikoski, 2010). From this perspective, bias, instability, and abstraction in agentic simulations do not constitute categorical objections. They instead highlight the need for transparent assumptions, bounded inference claims, and theory aligned evaluation. However, this parallel also implies accountability: if agentic simulations are to be treated as legitimate scientific instruments, they must meet the same standards of documentation, replication, and validity assessment that apply to established methods (Munafò et al., 2017).

5. Call to Action: Designing Socially Grounded Agentic Systems

Realizing the promise of multi agent LLM systems requires a reorientation in how agentic artificial intelligence is designed, evaluated, and deployed. Socially meaningful agentic systems cannot be engineered in isolation from social theory. They require explicit commitments about which social mechanisms are targeted, which boundary conditions are assumed, and which validity criteria warrant interpretation. We therefore propose the following steps.

- **For machine learning researchers: align architecture and evaluation with the targeted mechanism.** Move beyond optimizing isolated prompt performance toward multi agent architectures that support persistent state, goal pursuit, coordination, and environment coupling. For any claimed social mechanism, specify which architectural elements instantiate the mechanism and which elements are treated as assumptions. Complement task success metrics with interaction level and population level measures, such as memory consistency, coordination quality, resilience under perturbations, and stability across replications. Require replication across random seeds and sensitivity analysis as default practice when interpreting emergent patterns.
- **For social scientists: co design constructs, operationalizations, and validity criteria.** Engage directly in the design and evaluation of agentic systems by contributing theory grounded constructs, experimental paradigms, and measurement instruments. Specify what constitutes psychological validity and sociological validity for the targeted mechanism, and state inference limits explicitly. Use controlled perturbations and counterfactual interventions to test mechanisms, and distinguish between theory failure, model misspecification, and measurement error when results deviate from expectations.
- **For the research community and institutions: build shared standards, infrastructure, and governance.** Establish minimum reporting standards for agentic experiments, including environment specifications, interaction protocols, memory policies, objective definitions, safety constraints, and logging requirements. Develop shared benchmarks that evaluate interaction dynamics rather than only static outcomes, together with reproducible evaluation harnesses. Support interdisciplinary work through workshops, reviewing practices, and shared environment releases, and develop governance practices for open ended settings so that increased autonomy does not imply uncontrolled escalation.

By embracing these steps, the field can move beyond static text generation toward agentic systems capable of sustained interaction, coordination, and co evolution. The future of agentic artificial intelligence lies not in increasingly capable isolated models, but in socially grounded systems whose behavior is interpretable because it is theory aligned, methodologically transparent, and evaluated against explicit validity criteria.

References

- Anthis, J. R., Liu, R., Richardson, S. M., Kozlowski, A. C., Koch, B., Brynjolfsson, E., Evans, J., and Bernstein, M. S. Position: LLM Social Simulations Are a Promising Research Method. In *Forty-Second International Conference on Machine Learning Position Paper Track*, June 2025.
- Argyle, L. P., Busby, E. C., Fulda, N., Gubler, J. R., Rytting, C., and Wingate, D. Out of One, Many: Using Language Models to Simulate Human Samples. *Political Analysis*, 31(3):337–351, July 2023. ISSN 1047-1987, 1476-4989. doi: 10.1017/pan.2023.2.
- Bell, S. J., Kampman, O. P., Dodge, J., and Lawrence, N. D. Modeling the Machine Learning Multiverse, October 2022.
- Boiko, D. A., MacKnight, R., and Gomes, G. Emergent autonomous scientific research capabilities of large language models, April 2023. URL <http://arxiv.org/abs/2304.05332>. arXiv:2304.05332 [physics].
- Boyd, J. R. *A discourse on winning and losing*, volume 400. Air University Press Maxwell Air Force Base, AL, 2018. URL https://www.airuniversity.af.edu/Portals/10/AUPress/Books/B_0151_Boyd_Discourse_Winning_Losing.pdf.
- Cartwright, N. *Nature’s Capacities and Their Measurement*. Clarendon Press, 1989.
- Chen, J., Badshah, S., Yu, X., and Han, S. Static Sandboxes Are Inadequate: Modeling Societal Complexity Requires Open-Ended Co-Evolution in LLM-Based Multi-Agent Simulations, October 2025.
- Cummins, J. The threat of analytic flexibility in using large language models to simulate human data: A call to attention, September 2025.
- Dai, G., Zhang, W., Li, J., Yang, S., Ibe, C. O., Rao, S., Caetano, A., and Sra, M. Artificial Leviathan: Exploring Social Evolution of LLM Agents Through the Lens of Hobbesian Social Contract Theory, July 2024. URL <http://arxiv.org/abs/2406.14373>. arXiv:2406.14373 [cs].
- Demszky, D., Yang, D., Yeager, D. S., Bryan, C. J., Clapper, M., Chandhok, S., Eichstaedt, J. C., Hecht, C., Jamieson, J., Johnson, M., Jones, M., Krettek-Cobb, D., Lai, L., JonesMitchell, N., Ong, D. C., Dweck, C. S., Gross, J. J., and Pennebaker, J. W. Using large language models in psychology. *Nature Reviews Psychology*, 2(11):688–701, November 2023. ISSN 2731-0574. doi: 10.1038/s44159-023-00241-5. URL <https://www.nature.com/articles/s44159-023-00241-5>. Publisher: Nature Publishing Group.
- Elster, J. *Explaining Social Behavior: More Nuts and Bolts for the Social Sciences*. Cambridge University Press, 2015.
- Epstein, J. M. Agent-based computational models and generative social science. *Complexity*, 4(5):41–60, May 1999. ISSN 1076-2787, 1099-0526. doi: 10.1002/(SICI)1099-0526(199905/06)4:5<41::AID-CPLX9>3.0.CO;2-F. URL [https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1002/\(SICI\)1099-0526\(199905/06\)4:5<41::AID-CPLX9>3.0.CO;2-F](https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1002/(SICI)1099-0526(199905/06)4:5<41::AID-CPLX9>3.0.CO;2-F).
- Estornell, A. and Liu, Y. Multi-LLM Debate: Framework, Principals, and Interventions. In *38th Conference on Neural Information Processing Systems Proceedings*, 2024.
- Feng, S., Ding, W., Liu, A., Wang, Z., Shi, W., Wang, Y., Shen, Z., Han, X., Lang, H., Lee, C.-Y., Pfister, T., Choi, Y., and Tsvetkov, Y. When One LLM Drools, Multi-LLM Collaboration Rules, February 2025. URL <http://arxiv.org/abs/2502.04506>. arXiv:2502.04506 [cs].
- Gao, C., Lan, X., Lu, Z., Mao, J., Piao, J., Wang, H., Jin, D., and Li, Y. S3: Social-network Simulation System with Large Language Model-Empowered Agents, July 2023. URL <https://arxiv.org/abs/2307.14984v2>.
- Gelman, A. and Loken, E. The garden of forking paths: Why multiple comparisons can be a problem, even when there is no “fishing expedition” or “p-hacking” and the research hypothesis was posited ahead of time. *Department of Statistics, Columbia University*, 348(1-17):3, 2013.
- Guo, T., Chen, X., Wang, Y., Chang, R., Pei, S., Chawla, N. V., Wiest, O., and Zhang, X. Large Language Model based Multi-Agents: A Survey of Progress and Challenges, April 2024.
- Guozhen, Z., Zihan, Y., Nian, L., Fudan, Y., Qingyue, L., Depeng, J., and Yong, L. Human Behavior Simulation: Objectives, Methodologies, and Open Problems, November 2024.
- Haase, J. and Pokutta, S. Beyond Static Responses: Multi-Agent LLM Systems as a New Paradigm for Social Science Research, June 2025.
- Hardy, M., Sucholutsky, I., Thompson, B., and Griffiths, T. Large language models meet cognitive science: LLMs as tools, models, and participants. *Proceedings of the Annual Meeting of the Cognitive Science Society*, 45(45), 2023. URL <https://escholarship.org/uc/item/6dp9k2gz>.

- Hedström, P. and Ylikoski, P. Causal Mechanisms in the Social Sciences. *Annual Review of Sociology*, 36(1): 49–67, June 2010. ISSN 0360-0572, 1545-2115. doi: 10.1146/annurev.soc.012809.102632.
- Horton, J. J. Large Language Models as Simulated Economic Agents: What Can We Learn from Homo Siliacus?, April 2023. URL <https://www.nber.org/papers/w31122>.
- Kantor, J. Best practices for implementing ChatGPT, large language models, and artificial intelligence in qualitative and survey-based research. *JAAD International*, 14: 22–23, March 2024. ISSN 2666-3287, 2666-3287. doi: 10.1016/j.jdin.2023.10.001. URL [https://www.jaadinternational.org/article/S2666-3287\(23\)00157-8/fulltext](https://www.jaadinternational.org/article/S2666-3287(23)00157-8/fulltext). Publisher: Elsevier.
- Karjus, A. Machine-assisted quantizing designs: augmenting humanities and social sciences with artificial intelligence. *Humanities and Social Sciences Communications*, 12(1):1–18, February 2025. ISSN 2662-9992. doi: 10.1057/s41599-025-04503-w. URL <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41599-025-04503-w>. Publisher: Palgrave.
- Li, Y., Zhang, Y., and Sun, L. MetaAgents: Simulating Interactions of Human Behaviors for LLM-based Task-oriented Coordination via Collaborative Generative Agents, October 2023. URL <http://arxiv.org/abs/2310.06500>. arXiv:2310.06500 [cs].
- Lu, C., Lu, C., Lange, R. T., Foerster, J., Clune, J., and Ha, D. The AI Scientist: Towards Fully Automated Open-Ended Scientific Discovery, September 2024.
- Munafò, M. R., Nosek, B. A., Bishop, D. V. M., Button, K. S., Chambers, C. D., Percie du Sert, N., Simonsohn, U., Wagenmakers, E.-J., Ware, J. J., and Ioannidis, J. P. A. A manifesto for reproducible science. *Nature Human Behaviour*, 1(1):0021, January 2017. ISSN 2397-3374. doi: 10.1038/s41562-016-0021.
- Park, J. S., O’Brien, J., Cai, C. J., Morris, M. R., Liang, P., and Bernstein, M. S. Generative Agents: Interactive Simulacra of Human Behavior. In *Proceedings of the 36th Annual ACM Symposium on User Interface Software and Technology*, UIST ’23, pp. 1–22, New York, NY, USA, October 2023. Association for Computing Machinery. ISBN 979-8-4007-0132-0. doi: 10.1145/3586183.3606763. URL <https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3586183.3606763>.
- Piao, J., Yan, Y., Zhang, J., Li, N., Yan, J., Lan, X., Lu, Z., Zheng, Z., Wang, J. Y., Zhou, D., Gao, C., Xu, F., Zhang, F., Rong, K., Su, J., and Li, Y. AgentSociety: Large-Scale Simulation of LLM-Driven Generative Agents Advances Understanding of Human Behaviors and Society, February 2025.
- Piatti, G., Jin, Z., Kleiman-Weiner, M., Schölkopf, B., Sachan, M., and Mihalcea, R. Cooperate or Collapse: Emergence of Sustainable Cooperation in a Society of LLM Agents. *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems*, 37:111715–111759, December 2024.
- Sclar, M., Choi, Y., Tsvetkov, Y., and Suhr, A. Quantifying Language Models’ Sensitivity to Spurious Features in Prompt Design or: How I learned to start worrying about prompt formatting, July 2024.
- Simonsohn, U., Simmons, J. P., and Nelson, L. D. Specification curve analysis. *Nature Human Behaviour*, 4(11):1208–1214, November 2020. ISSN 2397-3374. doi: 10.1038/s41562-020-0912-z.
- Starace, G., Jaffe, O., Sherburn, D., Aung, J., Shern, C. J., Maksin, L., Dias, R., Mays, E., Kinsella, B., Thompson, W., Heidecke, J., Glaese, A., and Patwardhan, T. PaperBench: Evaluating AI’s Ability to Replicate AI Research, 2025.
- Tran, K.-T., Dao, D., Nguyen, M.-D., Pham, Q.-V., O’Sullivan, B., and Nguyen, H. D. Multi-Agent Collaboration Mechanisms: A Survey of LLMs, January 2025.
- Wang, L., Ma, C., Feng, X., Zhang, Z., Yang, H., Zhang, J., Chen, Z., Tang, J., Chen, X., Lin, Y., Zhao, W. X., Wei, Z., and Wen, J. A survey on large language model based autonomous agents. *Frontiers of Computer Science*, 18(6):186345, March 2024. ISSN 2095-2236. doi: 10.1007/s11704-024-40231-1. URL <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11704-024-40231-1>.
- Xu, Y., Wang, S., Li, P., Luo, F., Wang, X., Liu, W., and Liu, Y. Exploring Large Language Models for Communication Games: An Empirical Study on Werewolf, May 2024. URL <http://arxiv.org/abs/2309.04658>. arXiv:2309.04658 [cs].
- Zhang, Y., Diddee, H., Holm, S., Liu, H., Liu, X., Samuel, V., Wang, B., and Ippolito, D. NoveltyBench: Evaluating Language Models for Humanlike Diversity, August 2025.
- Ziems, C., Held, W., Shaikh, O., Chen, J., Zhang, Z., and Yang, D. Can large language models transform computational social science? *Computational Linguistics*, 50(1): 237–291, 2024. URL https://direct.mit.edu/coli/article-pdf/doi/10.1162/coli_a_00502/2332904/coli_a_00502.pdf.